

**RISKS AND FACTORS ASSOCIATED WITH THE DEVELOPMENT OF
DELIRIUM IN INTENSIVE CARE PATIENTS: BIBLIOGRAPHICAL
REVIEW**

 DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10359698

Ingrid Grazielly Felix Araujo

*Medical Student at Centro Universitário Maurício de Nassau, Recife-PE, Brazil;
ingridfaraujo01@gmail.com*

André Felipe Magalhães de Albuquerque

*Medical Student at Centro Universitário Maurício de Nassau, Recife-PE, Brazil; Email:
afmagalhaesa@gmail.com*

Antonio Luna e Silva

*Medical Student at Centro Universitário Maurício de Nassau, Recife-PE, Brazil; Email:
lunaesilva@hotmail.com*

Gabriel Luiz de Castro Nascimento

*Medical Student at Centro Universitário Maurício de Nassau, Recife-PE, Brazil; Email:
gabrielluizcn@hotmail.com*

João Victor Gomes Pereira de Barros

*Medical Student at Faculdade Pernambucana de Saúde, Recife-PE, Brazil;
Email: joaovitor.pa@hotmail.com*

Paulo José Tavares de Lima

*Master's degree in Neuropsychiatry from the Federal University of Pernambuco, preceptor at
the Centro Universitário Maurício de Nassau, Recife, Pernambuco, Brazil;
Email: paulojtlima@gmail.com*

ABSTRACT

Introduction : Delirium is an acute neurological disorder frequently observed in patients , especially elderly people , at intensive Care Units (ICU), and is characterized by transient changes in consciousness and cognition . Patients who develop this disorder had worse clinical performance, which contributes to longer hospital stays and an increased incidence of unfavorable clinical outcomes , leading to high morbidity and mortality . **Objective :** The aim of this study was to carry out a literature review on the risks and factors associated with the development of delirium in intensive care patients . **Methodology :** A bibliographical survey was carried out between 2006 and 2020 in the Scielo , PubMed , PubMed and VHL databases . The descriptors used : Delirium, Confusion and intensive Care Unit. **Results :** Delirium is a disturbance of attention and consciousness followed by variation in cognition , within the literature it is possible to find that the problem affects a significant rate of ICU patients , reaching an incidence of up to 89%, thus doubling the mortality rates in these patients . Furthermore , the diagnosis of delirium in critically ill patients is associated with increased time on mechanical ventilation , length of stay in the ICU and associated comorbidities . Delirium can lead to aggravating circumstances such as removal of invasive equipment , self-extubation and cognitive sequelae . **Conclusion :** Knowledge of the risk factors for delirium in patients in intensive care by professionals is of crucial importance only that this neurological condition can be prevented , as well as early diagnosis and effective treatment can be achieved in order to improve the prognosis of these patients .

Keywords: Delirium. Confusion . intensive Care Unit.

INTRODUCTION

Delirium is an acute confusional state associated with increased mortality in the intensive care unit (ICU) with compromised long-term functional recovery. This condition has a high prevalence in critically ill patients, bringing several adverse clinical results. Current guidelines for medical practice recommend that ICU patients should be routinely screened for delirium. Although it is currently known by health professionals, it is still frequently underdiagnosed, with care being less specific, determining its multifactorial aspect, involving a high rate of risks involving the development of this clinical syndrome.

GOAL

Understand the relevance of early diagnosis of delirium in ICU patients, knowing the predisposing factors of this condition and the risks of its development.

METHODOLOGY

A bibliographic review was carried out, based on searches for articles in databases such

as Scielo , PubMed , PebMed and VHL, using the knowledge available in full on the topic.

RESULTS

Delirium is a disturbance of attention and consciousness followed by variation in cognition that is not clearly caused by dementia or is developing. Furthermore, several studies prove that the problem affects a significant rate of ICU patients, in addition to the fact that patients who have had delirium have a mortality rate twice as high. Furthermore, the diagnosis of delirium in critically ill patients is associated with increased time on mechanical ventilation, length of stay in the ICU and hospital and as seen before mortality. These patients may experience complications during their stay in the ICU, such as removal of invasive devices and self-extubation , with delirium also responsible for long-term cognitive and emotional sequelae, including up to six months after hospital discharge. Delirium develops over a short period of time , fluctuating throughout the day, and its development is linked to several factors, causes generally experienced in ICUs. In addition to the patient's non-modifiable risk factors, there are modifiable clinical and environmental aspects that must be evaluated to reduce the occurrence and severity of delirium, such as serious infections, acute changes in organ function, mechanical ventilation, the use of sedatives and psychotropic medications. , predispose the patient to delirium. However, screening must be carried out so that delirium can be identified, it needs to be investigated and, as it is a clinical syndrome, its diagnosis must be made at the bedside, for better therapeutic guidance of the patient and prognostic vision.

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

At the intensive care level, early diagnosis and monitoring of delirium is extremely important, being related to the prevention of adverse events, in addition to being an indicator of organic dysfunction. In short, the reduction in incidence needs to be prioritized as a quality parameter at the ICU level, demonstrating the improvement in the advancement of patient care. Therefore, safe care is promoted, allowing the implementation of preventive and therapeutic measures for better rehabilitation and potential reduction in losses related to this condition.

REFERENCES**Articles:**

SILVA, MHO DA et al. Delirium in intensive care: predisposing factors and prevention of adverse events. **Rev. Bahia Enferm** , p. e26031–e26031, 2018.

PESSOA, RF; NÁCUL, FE Delirium in critically ill patients. **Brazilian Journal of Intensive Care** , v. 18, no. 2, Jun. 2006.

MORI, S. et al. Incidence and factors related I'm delirium in an intensive care unit . USP **Nursing School Magazine** , v. 50, no. 4, p. 587–593, 1 Jul. 2016.

CASTRO, REV DE. **Delirium in Intensive Care Units** : what we need to know. Available at: < <https://pebmed.com.br/delirium-em-unidades-de-terapia-intensiva-o-que-precisamos-saber/> >.

Gaúcha Nursing Magazine . [sl : sn]. Available at:
<<https://www.scielo.br/j/rngenf/a/G3NvgqBC5DM5tFFS8LSp9ht/?format=pdf&lang=pt>>.